

1 **A liver organoid model of HBV infection.**

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6 Hepatitis B virus is a causative factor in inflammatory disease and cancer. We studied HBV infection in a
7 novel organoid culture system, monitoring the cellular response to infection by measuring total
8 transcription by RNA-sequencing. We describe here using this technology silencing of the TNF receptor
9 *Tnfrsf1b* during hepatitis B infection.

10 Citations

11 1. De Crignis, E., Hossain, T., Romal, S., Carofiglio, F., Moulos, P., Khalid, M.M., Rao, S.,
12 Bazrafshan, A., Verstegen, M.M., Pourfarzad, F. and Koutsothanassis, C., 2021. Application of human liver
13 organoids as a patient-derived primary model for HBV infection and related hepatocellular carcinoma.
14 *Elife*, 10, p.e60747.

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